

Preliminary Design of the Propulsion Subsystem for the European Advanced Reusable Satellite (EARS)

Lorenzo Gerolin ^{*} and Giulia Quinzi [†]

Technology for Propulsion and Innovation, Via Emilia 15, Monselice (PD), 35043, Italy

Francesco Barato [‡]

Università degli Studi di Padova, Via Venezia 1, Padova, 35131, Italy

The European Advanced Reusable Satellite (EARS) is a European Commission funded program that aims at designing a reusable microsat to deliver commercial, scientific and institutional payloads to LEO and retrieving them back safely on Earth. The program seeks to develop the key enabling technologies for the foreseen mission. In this frame, T4i is designing the propulsion subsystem for the satellite and is developing the HTP and propane fed bipropellant thruster. The propulsion subsystem is responsible for delivering a precise de-orbit burn using 4 engines that rely on differential steering to keep the thrust vector aligned with the velocity vector. Differential steering is obtained through the thrusters' pulsed mode where their nominal bi-propellant working mode is switched temporarily to a mono-propellant one by shutting off the fuel feeding valve. While this procedure slightly reduces the average specific impulse delivered by the platform, it allows for a simple and robust two axis control of the spacecraft during firing. A third controlling element, a propane cold gas reaction control system, was identified as the best solution for controlling rotations around the roll axis.

I. Nomenclature

A. Acronyms

<i>AOCS</i>	=	Attitude and Orbit Control System
<i>BP</i>	=	Bi-propellant
<i>CNR</i>	=	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
<i>CG</i>	=	Cold Gas
<i>CM</i>	=	Center of Mass
<i>CONOPS</i>	=	Concept of Operations
<i>DES</i>	=	Deimos Space
<i>DS</i>	=	Differential Steering
<i>EARS</i>	=	European Advanced Reusable Satellite
<i>EOL</i>	=	End Of Life
<i>GNC</i>	=	Guidance, Navigation and Control
<i>HTP</i>	=	High Test Peroxide
<i>KNA</i>	=	Kongsberg NanoAvionics
<i>LEO</i>	=	Low Earth Orbit

^{*}Project Manager, R&D Engineer, Liquid Propulsion, AIAA member

[†]R&D Engineer, Liquid Propulsion

[‡]Researcher, Department of Industrial Engineering, AIAA member

MP = Mono-propellant
RCS = Reaction Control System
T4i = Technology for Propulsion and Innovation
UNIPD = University of Padova
VKI = Von Karman Institute for Fluid Dynamics

B. Symbols

d = Distance
D = Duty cycle
g = Standard gravity acceleration
I = Impulse or moment of Inertia
l = Length
m = Mass
n = Number of thrusters
 \dot{m} = Mass Flow
O/F = Oxidizer over Fuel ratio
T = Thrust
t = Time
w = Width
 α = Misalignment of thrust axis with respect to nominal thrust axis
 θ = Rotation angle
 τ = Torque
 ω = Rotational speed

C. Superscripts

eq = Equivalent
N = Nominal

D. Subscripts

0 = Reference
a = Axial
avg = Average
B = Bi-propellant or Satellite Body Reference System
c = Control
cg = Cold Gas
dis = Disturb
l = Lateral
M = Monopropellant
p = Propellant
S = Satellite
sp = Specific
t = Thruster
TOT = Total
v = Valve
x = x Axis Direction
y = y Axis Direction
z = z Axis Direction

II. Introduction

The New Space Economy is pushing towards sustainability, cost reduction and lower times to orbit to create the next generation of launchers and space vehicles. In particular, the new paradigm of reusability is recently gaining traction. EARS was born in this frame as a recoverable and reusable microsatellite capable of delivering small payloads to LEO [1]. The program, under the coordination of Italian CNR, sees as consortium partners UNIPD for the system level studies [2], DES for the mission analysis and re-entry GNC algorithm, while KNA is in charge of the main platform, VKI of the re-entry inflatable heat shield, and T4i of the propulsion subsystem. The propulsion module allows for the precise de-orbiting burn and other orbital maneuvers, including station keeping. The reference satellite onto which EARS is being designed is KNA MP42 (fig. 1 and 2). The MP42 platform allows for subsystems expansions, which in EARS case are the addition of two separate modules as can be seen in fig. 3 and 4. The upper module is the inflatable heat shield subsystem. The shield nose is made of a ceramic matrix composite which will allow for its reusability after protecting the whole satellite during the atmospheric re-entry phase. The lower module contains instead the propulsion and recovery subsystems. As well as the storage of all propane and HTP tanks with their own respective fluidic elements, this module is going to accommodate the satellite parafoil, which will be deployed after re-entry to ensure a slow guided descent towards Earth until finally the spacecraft is retrieved in mid-air by an helicopter. Delving deeper into the propulsion module, the choice is to employ liquid bi-propellant rocket engines. Solid rockets were discarded for the safety aspects of pyrotechnics and the impossibility to control thrust. Moreover, considering that typical burning times for small solid rockets are in the dozens of seconds, the thrust would have been too high for misalignment to be compensated by the satellite AOCS. Hybrid rocket motors were discarded too due the relatively low thrust-long burning time scenario, which is hardly managed by such systems [3] [4]. A competitive solution that challenges BP engines are MP ones, which are simpler and require less relative inert mass. On a case such as the EARS one, the total impulse to be delivered requires an important amount of propellant mass. This amount could be almost halved considering that a BP engine fed with HTP has roughly a double I_{sp} compared to the MP one. On the BP case, the relative increased amount of inert mass is way lower than the saving on the total mass, thus making the BP solution the most viable for EARS satellite. Differential steering was chosen for EARS to ensure that during engines firing the satellite will keep the correct attitude. By adopting this technical solution, the satellite can mount standard AOCS devices like reaction wheels and/or magnetorquers for in-orbit operations, keeping the authority of these device limited to orbital disturbances compensation and to non-firing attitude management. The much higher torques that are developed by the bipropellant thrusters are managed by the thrusters themselves. This solution can be put in place pulsing the fuel flow on the BP thruster, halving the I_{sp} and thus the thrust, generating proper active control torques on the spacecraft.

The EARS propulsion technology employs green propellants to keep costs, environmental impact and operations to a minimum. High concentration hydrogen peroxide is selected as oxidizer because of its availability at moderate cost, high density, the possibility to be stored for months in space at moderate pressures and the possibility to be decomposed in a catalyst bed without pre-heating, allowing for both MP and staged combustion BP [5]. Propane has been selected as a fuel for its wide availability at low cost, good performance and moderate self-pressurization capability at room temperature. Moreover, self-pressurization allows for a two-fluids-only approach, that eliminates the need for a pressurizing gas and related equipment like pressure regulators [6].

Regarding thrust ranges for the EARS spacecraft, a trade-off was done between different scales of the thruster, where a higher size generally means better performances, lower gravity losses and better internal heat management but also means higher acceleration on the payload, larger dimensions and more difficult heat management for the platform, higher torques and lower response speeds. The result for EARS has been a total thrust of 40 N, which is indeed the thrust that will be investigated further later on.

This paper will present the design choices behind the positioning of the thrusters and cold gas RCS with a particular consideration towards the efficient use of propellants in the system. Two main solutions have been compared, configuration A with a single central 40 N thruster and configuration B with four 10 N separated thrusters.

Fig. 1 MP42 Payload Envelope. Satellite height is highly adjustable to customers payload requirements, up to 1300 mm (Courtesy of KNA [7]).

Fig. 2 MP42 bottom view with the 15'' deployment ring (Courtesy of KNA [7]).

Fig. 3 EARS satellite concept derived from KNA MP42 platform with the addition of top and bottom modules.

Fig. 4 EARS spacecraft rendering during in orbit mission operations.

III. Preliminary Definitions

Two fundamental equations must be defined in order to better understand the comparison procedure. The first is the equivalent specific impulse, defined as the total delivered impulse in the axial direction divided by the total used propellant to deliver such impulse, including attitude control, normalized with g_0 as in the "standard" specific impulse formulation.

$$I_{sp}^{eq} = \frac{I_{TOT}}{m_p^{TOT} \cdot g_0} \quad (1)$$

The second equation is the equivalent specific impulse ratio, defined as:

$$r = \frac{I_{sp}^{eq}}{I_{sp}^N} = \frac{I_{sp}^{eq}}{I_{sp.B}} = \frac{m_p^N}{m_p^{TOT}} \quad (2)$$

where I_{sp}^N is the nominal specific impulse of the thruster. The equivalent specific impulse ratio is a number lower than one and it is a measure of how less performing the propulsion system is with respect to the nominal case without wasting any propellant for the disturbance correction. The equivalent specific impulse pertains to situations where thrusters with different specific impulses generate thrust along distinct directions, allowing to calculate a single, effective specific impulse that represents the combined performance of all thrusters working together with respect to the direction of advancement.

Differently from the equivalent specific impulse, the mean specific impulse comes into play when thrusters with different specific impulses are creating thrust in the same direction. In this case, the mean specific impulse provides an overall average performance measure for the propulsion system in the direction of the thrust, which could not be the one of the velocity.

Two arrangements of the thrusters were initially taken into account and the following sections will be focused into describing both of them and evaluating which one is more adequate. In order to do so, a specific system of reference has been chosen: the centre is fixed on the centre of mass of the system, the x_B axis is aligned with the motion direction and y_B and z_B axes are oriented in order to define a leftwards orthogonal set of three.

IV. Engine Configuration A: Single Central 40 N Engine

The first idea is to use a single engine, generating a thrust force of 40 N and employing a series of cold gas thrusters to perform the attitude control. The thruster is positioned centrally on the face of the satellite that contains the ring adapter. The two main sources of disturbances are:

- **the misalignment d of the centre of mass:** the effect is the generation of a torque around y_B and/or z_B axis, depending on how the position of the centre of mass is intended. Therefore, the torques can be calculated as:

$$\begin{cases} \tau_y = T \cdot d_z \\ \tau_z = T \cdot d_y \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where T is the force generated by the propulsive module, and d_z and d_y are the misalignments of the centre of mass respectively along z_B and y_B axis;

- **the thrust misalignment:** it is intended as a deviation of the thrust direction of an angle α with respect to the nominal one. Therefore, two thrust components can be distinguished, an axial one and a lateral one:

$$\begin{cases} T_a = T \cdot \cos \alpha \\ T_l = T \cdot \sin \alpha \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

If the effect of the misalignment of the centre of mass is combined with the one of thrust, multiple torques are generated. Torques seen in Eq. (3) turn into:

$$\begin{cases} \tau_y = T_a \cdot d_z \\ \tau_z = T_a \cdot d_y \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

At the same time T_l is responsible for the generation of the following torques:

$$\begin{cases} \tau_x = T_l \cdot d \\ \tau_y = T_l \cdot \frac{l}{2} \\ \tau_z = T_l \cdot \frac{l}{2} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where τ_x causes the system to roll. From now on only τ_y will be mentioned, knowing that τ_z can be controlled in the exact same way.

A. Control strategies for y_B -axis torque

A control force T_c to counterbalance τ_y can be imparted positioning the CG thrusters in different manners. Three configurations have been investigated:

- 1) *First configuration:*

This configuration comprises two CG thrusters, arranged with a lever arm equal to l as it can be seen in Fig. 5. The forces defining the couple are opposed and thus they do not participate in any translation of the system.

Fig. 5 First collocation of the cold gas thrusters for torque control around y_B axis.

Table 1 First configuration key performance equations.

Control Force	$T_c = \frac{\tau_y}{l}$	(7a)
Equivalent Specific Impulse	$I_{sp}^{eq} = \frac{T_a}{\frac{T_a}{I_{sp}^N} + \frac{2 \cdot T_c}{I_{sp,cg}}}$	(7b)
Equivalent Specific Impulse Ratio	$r = \frac{1}{1 + 2 \cdot \frac{T_c}{T_a} \cdot \frac{I_{sp}^N}{I_{sp,cg}}}$	(7c)

In Table (1), I_{sp}^N is the specific impulse of the main thruster, while $I_{sp,cg}$ is the one of the cold gas thrusters employed for the attitude control. The equivalent specific impulse ratio, as seen in Eq. (2), is obtained by dividing the equivalent specific impulse by the nominal specific impulse of the thruster.

2) Second configuration:

This configuration involves a single cold gas thruster, as it can be seen in the figure below. Differently from the previous one, this configuration is not balanced, in fact the torque is compensated via a single force, which consequently induces a translation of the system along the direction of the force. However, it is easier to pack in the propulsion submodule, which is placed on the bottom of the spacecraft.

Fig. 6 Second collocation of the cold gas thrusters for torque control around y_B -axis.

Table 2 Second configuration key performance equations.

Control Force	$T_c = \frac{\tau_y}{l/2}$	(8a)
Equivalent Specific Impulse	$I_{sp}^{eq} = \frac{T_a}{\frac{T_a}{I_{sp}^N} + \frac{T_c}{I_{sp.cg}}}$	(8b)
Equivalent Specific Impulse Ratio	$r = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{T_c}{T_a} \cdot \frac{I_{sp}^N}{I_{sp.cg}}}$	(8c)

3) *Third configuration:*

As in the previous case, there is a single cold gas thruster. In this configuration it is however generating a control force along the nominal direction. It follows that the equivalent specific ratio equals the mean specific ratio.

Fig. 7 Third collocation of the cold gas thrusters for torque control around y_B -axis.

Table 3 Third configuration key performance equations.

Control Force	$T_c = \frac{\tau_y}{\frac{w}{2} - d}$	(9a)
Equivalent Specific Impulse	$I_{sp}^{eq} = \frac{T_a + T_c}{\frac{T_a}{I_{sp}^N} + \frac{T_c}{I_{sp,cg}}}$	(9b)
Equivalent Specific Impulse Ratio	$r = \frac{1 + \frac{T_c}{T_a}}{1 + \frac{T_c}{T_a} \cdot \frac{I_{sp}^N}{I_{sp,cg}}}$	(9c)

For each configuration that has been analysed, the total mass of propellant that needs to be spent including the one to counteract the attitude deviation can be computed inserting the previous expressions for the equivalent specific impulse I_{sp}^{eq} in Eq. 1:

$$m_p^{TOT} = \frac{I_{TOT}}{I_{sp}^{eq} \cdot g_0} \quad (10)$$

where I_{TOT} represents the axial total impulse, which is defined as a mission requirement.

In the third configuration, because of the cold gas thruster acting along the nominal thrust direction, the mass penalty is only due to the fact that the cold gas thruster is less performing than the bipropellant one. In fact, from Eq. (9b) it can be seen that the equivalent specific impulse is equal to the nominal specific impulse if $I_{sp,cg} = I_{sp}^N$. On the other hand, if the first two configurations are considered, the condition $I_{sp}^{eq} = I_{sp}^N$ is satisfied exclusively when $I_{sp,cg}$ approaches infinity. This occurs due to the non-coinciding directions of thrust between the cold gas thruster and the main thruster. In other words, the cold gas thruster is wasting propellant without actively contributing to the nominal thrust.

B. Control strategies for x_B axis torque

The difference of the control on this axis with respect to the other two is that no cold gas thruster configuration aligned with the main 40 N direction is capable of counteracting roll motion. The result is that this situation is very much similar to the one presented in the first configuration.

This is the reason why for this axis, rotation is controlled via two cold gas thrusters arranged as shown in Fig. 8. The control force is equal to:

$$T_c = \frac{\tau_x}{w} \quad (11)$$

while the equivalent specific impulse and the equivalent specific impulse ratio formulas are equal to Eqs. (7b) and (7c) respectively.

Fig. 8 Collocation of the cold gas thrusters for torque control around x_B -axis.

V. Engine Configuration B: Four 10 N Engines

Differently from the previous case, the nominal thrust is now split in four equal 10 N contributions generated by four bipropellant thrusters arranged at the corners of a square with side equal to $d_t = 0.4 m$. This measure is based on launch ring adapter, which has a diameter of 15 inches (381 mm). The reason behind this choice of thrust subdivision is the exploitation of the differential steering mode to obtain the desired attitude control. It means that thrust is being controlled by switching on and off the fuel firing valve, in order to generate pitch and yaw couples which orient the satellite during firing. This solution has been deemed to be the most practical and fast at this thruster size.

Due to the thrust misalignment of α , both T_M and T_B , which are the monopropellant and bipropellant thrusts, can be decomposed as:

$$\begin{cases} T_{B,a} = T_B \cdot \cos \alpha \\ T_{B,l} = T_B \cdot \sin \alpha \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

$$\begin{cases} T_{M,a} = T_M \cdot \cos \alpha \\ T_{M,l} = T_M \cdot \sin \alpha \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

Now the main disturbances examined will be presented, as well as the control strategies to counteract them.

A. T_l parallel to the satellite sides plus misaligned centre of mass

The axial thrust component (Fig. 9) produces a single torque around the y_B -axis, while the lateral thrust component (Fig. 9) is responsible for two torques: the first one around the y_B -axis and the second one around the x_B -axis:

$$\begin{cases} \tau_x = 2T_{B,l} \left(\frac{d_t}{2} + d \right) - 2T_{B,l} \left(\frac{d_t}{2} - d \right) = 4T_l \cdot d \\ \tau_y = 2T_{B,a} \left(\frac{w}{2} + d \right) - 2T_{B,a} \left(\frac{w}{2} - d \right) = 4T_{B,a} \cdot d \\ \tau_z = 4T_{B,l} \frac{l}{2} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

On y_B -axis two thrusters will function in MP mode and those who remain will work in BP mode. The thrusters intended to switch in the MP mode will be the furthest ones from the misaligned centre of mass. Moreover, in calculating the control torque, given that the misalignment of the centre of mass d is considered very small, it can be neglected, yielding for this case:

$$\tau_t = (n_B T_{B,a} - n_M T_{M,a}) \frac{d_t}{2} \quad (15)$$

where n_B and n_M are the number of thrusters operating in BP mode and in MP mode respectively. In this specific control strategy $n_B = 2$ and $n_M = 2$.

It is also possible to approximately compute the angle θ_y swept by the satellite around the y_B -axis after a single action of the fuel valve for a time t_v :

$$\theta_y = \frac{1}{2} \dot{\omega}_y t_v^2 \quad (16)$$

where the angular acceleration around y_B -axis can be obtained as:

$$\dot{\omega}_y = \frac{\tau_c}{I_S} \quad (17)$$

and the moment of inertia around the y_B -axis is:

$$I_S = \frac{1}{12} m_S (l^2 + w^2) \quad (18)$$

with m_S the mass of the satellite. Finally, the angular velocity is thus computed by multiplying the angular acceleration by the fuel valve timing:

$$\omega_y = \dot{\omega}_y \cdot t_v \quad (19)$$

For what concern the control strategy for x_B -axis, the same principle seen with the first engine configuration is adopted: two cold-gas thrusters are arranged as in Fig. 8, generating a thrust force equal to Eq. (11)

Fig. 9 From left to right: thrust lateral component arrangement, thrust axial component arrangement, control strategy for torques around y_B -axis.

B. T_l 'diagonally' oriented plus misaligned centre of mass

The thrust lateral component oriented as in Fig. 10 and the misalignment of the centre of mass produce the following torques:

$$\begin{cases} \tau_{zy} = 4T_{B,a} \cdot d \\ \tau_{zy} = 4T_{B,l} \cdot \frac{l}{2} \\ \tau_x = 4T_{B,l} \cdot d \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

where the first two equations are obtained combining τ_y and τ_z as two orthogonal vectors.

The control strategy adopted to counteract τ_{zy} consists in switching a single thruster to the MP mode, as it can be seen in Fig. 10. The assertion that the misalignment of the centre of mass d can be disregarded in the calculation of the control torque remains valid. Consequently, the control torque is simply given by:

$$\tau_t = (n_B T_{B,a} - n_M T_{M,a}) \frac{d_t}{2} \sqrt{2} \quad (21)$$

where $n_B = 1$ and $n_M = 1$.

For what concerns τ_x , the same thing applies as seen for the case of $T_{B,l}$ axially oriented.

Fig. 10 From left to right: thrust lateral component arrangement, control strategy for torques around y_B -axis.

C. T_l worst case for τ_x

In this case $T_{B,l}$ is oriented as in Fig. 11 and it generates the highest torque around x_B -axis of those examined so far:

$$\tau_x = 4T_{B,l} \frac{d_t}{2} \sqrt{2} \quad (22)$$

The control strategy is the same as the one seen for the previous torques around x_B axis, i.e. cold-gas thrusters.

Fig. 11 From left to right: worst case thrust lateral component arrangement for torques around x_B -axis, corresponding control strategy.

D. Equivalent propellant mass and equivalent specific impulse

In order to compensate a certain disturbance, the integral of the torques acting on the satellite over the total burning time t_{TOT} must equal the one of the control torques acting on the satellite over the time spent by the thrusters in mono-propellant mode t_M . Therefore, the ensuing relation follows:

$$\tau_t \cdot t_M = \tau_{dis} \cdot t_{TOT} \quad (23)$$

The ratio between the time spent by the thrusters in MP mode t_M and the total burning time t_{TOT} is the duty cycle D , which represents how long the thrusters operate in MP mode compared to the entire burning time, comprehensive of both the times spent by the engines in MP and BP mode. In other words, the burning time that appears in the duty cycle is not the nominal one defined initially for sizing purposes, but it will be higher because, as the engines will switch into a less efficient mode, they will not constantly generate the nominal thrust, but at the same time the axial total impulse must be constant, so the burning time will be increased to compensate the decrease in thrust. Obviously, the higher the number of thrusters switching to MP mode is, the higher will be the burning time increment. From the previous relation the duty cycle expression follows:

$$D = \frac{\tau_{dis}}{\tau_t} \quad (24)$$

In order to determine the actual burning time, the average thrust of the propulsive system must be computed first:

$$T_{avg} = n_B T_{B,a} + n_M T_{M,a} \cdot (1 - D) + n_M T_{M,a} \cdot D \quad (25)$$

in which the three terms stand for:

- 1) the thrust contribution by the number of thrusters that always work in bipropellant mode;
- 2) the thrust contribution by the number of thrusters that can switch to monopropellant, accounted for the time they work in bipropellant mode;
- 3) the thrust contribution by the number of thrusters that can switch to monopropellant, accounted for the time they work in monopropellant mode.

Consequently, the actual burning time and the time spent by the thrusters in monopropellant mode are respectively:

$$t_{TOT} = \frac{I_{TOT}}{T_{avg}} \quad (26)$$

$$t_M = D \cdot t_{TOT} \quad (27)$$

Once the duty cycle has been defined, the equivalent propellant mass in case of a torque around y_B -axis can be calculated as:

$$m_p^{TOT} = \frac{n_B T_B}{I_{sp,B} \cdot g_0} \cdot t_{TOT} + \frac{n_M T_B}{I_{sp,B} \cdot g_0} \cdot (1 - D) \cdot t_{TOT} + \frac{n_M T_M}{I_{sp,M} \cdot g_0} \cdot D \cdot t_{TOT} \quad (28)$$

In which the three terms account in the same way as the three terms of Eq. (25).

In the case of controlling a disturbance around x_B -axis with cold-gas thrusters, the equivalent propellant mass is:

$$m_p^{TOT} = \frac{I_{TOT}}{I_{sp,B} \cdot g_0} + \frac{2T_{control} \cdot t_{TOT}}{I_{sp,cg} \cdot g_0} \quad (29)$$

Obviously the equivalent specific impulse and the equivalent specific impulse ratio are respectively derived as follow:

$$\begin{cases} I_{sp}^{eq} = \frac{I_{TOT}}{m_p^{TOT} \cdot g_0} \\ r = \frac{I_{sp}^{eq}}{I_{sp}^N} \end{cases} \quad (30)$$

VI. Best configuration selection

Numerical elaboration of the models just presented will now be shown. In the following table the main initial data are summed up:

Table 4 Numerical simulation data.

Center of mass misalignment [mm]	10
Maximum RW momentum [Nms]	1
Misalignment α [°]	0.25
Satellite Mass [kg]	120
Length of Spacecraft [m]	1
Width of Spacecraft [m]	0.5
Spacing Between Thrusters [m]	0.4
Thrust, Single Bipropellant Thruster [N]	10
Specific Impulse, Nominal of Thruster, Bipropellant Mode [s]	300
Specific Impulse, Nominal of Thruster, Monopropellant Mode [s]	150
Specific Impulse, Nominal of Cold Gas Thrusters [s]	60
Time, Nominal Burn [s]	600
Timing, Fuel Valve [ms]	30
O/F [#]	7

For each disturbance taken into account, it was checked if its integral over the burning time exceeded the maximum momentum of the reaction wheel. If the angular momentum can be thoroughly absorbed by the reaction wheel (i.e. its maximum allowable momentum is higher than the actual disturbance integral), then the thruster solution may be unnecessary. Otherwise thrusters must be kept into consideration as the primary solution to compensate the disturbances.

A. Configuration A, Single Central 40 N Engine

From Table 5, it can be seen that both torques around y_B -axis and the one around x_B -axis require the cold-gas thrusters intervention. Moreover, as regard the y_B -axis control techniques, from Table 6 and Table 7 it can be deduced that the control configuration with only one cold-gas thruster acting along the nominal motion direction is not the most efficient in this case, if compared with the other two, because even though the cold-gas thruster is generating a force in the same direction of the main engine, it suffers from a shorter arm that generates a lower torque. If the most severe torque is considered, that is the one around the y_B -axis due to T_{axial} , for the one or two 'lateral thrusters' control technique the penalty on the nominal specific impulse of about 9% is quite high. On the other hand, the penalty on the nominal specific impulse for what concerns the x_B -axis control technique is only the 0.1%, as the torque around the x_B -axis is very small if compared with those around the y_B -axis.

Table 5 Torques and their integral over burning time for first engine configuration.

	τ [mNm]	$\int \tau dt$ [Nms]
Around y_B -axis due to T_{axial}	400	240
Around y_B -axis due to T_l	87.3	52.4
Around x_B -axis due to T_l	1.70	1.02

Table 6 Equivalent propellant mass, equivalent specific impulse and equivalent specific impulse ratio obtained in counteracting the torque around y_B -axis (with different control techniques) due to the thrust axial component in the the three different engine configurations.

τ_y due to T_{axial}	m_p^{TOT} [kg]	I_{sp}^{eq} [s]	r [%]
Two Lateral Thrusters	8.97	273	90.9
One Lateral Thruster	8.97	273	90.9
One Axial Thruster	9.46	259	86.2

Table 7 Equivalent propellant mass, equivalent specific impulse and equivalent specific impulse ratio obtained in counteracting the torque around y_B -axis (with different control techniques) due to the thrust lateral component in the first engine configuration.

τ_y due to T_l	m_p^{TOT} [kg]	I_{sp}^{eq} [s]	r [%]
Two Lateral Thrusters	8.33	294	97.9
One Lateral Thruster	8.33	294	97.9
One Axial Thruster	8.45	290	96.5

Table 8 Equivalent propellant mass, equivalent specific impulse and equivalent specific impulse ratio obtained in counteracting the torque around x_B -axis due to the thrust lateral component in the first engine configuration.

τ_x due to T_l	m_p^{TOT} [kg]	I_{sp}^{eq} [s]	r [%]
Two Lateral Thrusters	8.16	299.7	99.9

B. Configuration B, Four 10 N Engines

The magnitude of the disturbing torques is the same of the one analysed in the first engine configuration, with the exception of the additional worst case around the x_B -axis. Again, the torque integral of each disturbance taken into account is higher than the maximum momentum allowed by the reaction wheel, as it can be seen from Table 9. Regarding the control of the torques around the y_B -axis, it can be seen from Table 10 and Table 11 that in the worst case, that is the one of the torque caused by T_{axial} , the reduction in the nominal specific impulse is about 4% and 3% respectively for the control technique involving two and only one thruster switching to MP mode. Obviously, this result is below the reduction of 9% provided by the first engine configuration with the best control technique. For what concerns the torques around the x_B -axis caused by T_l , the second engine configuration presents a higher propellant mass penalty related to the worst case of T_l direction; however, the specific impulse reduction of 2.4% is still much lower than the maximum one seen in the first engine configuration.

It must be noted that the total average thrust produced by the engines is below the nominal 40 N and, consequently, the actual burning time must slightly increase to meet the mission requirement on axial total impulse.

Concluding, the four engines configuration has been selected for the EARS propulsion system because of the lower losses incurred with the active compensation of disturbances.

Table 9 Torques and their integral over burning time for second engine configuration.

	τ [mNm]	$\int \tau dt$ [Nms]
Around y_B -axis due to T_a	400	240
Around y_B -axis due to T_l	87.3	52.4
Around x_B -axis due to T_l	1.70	1.02
Around x_B -axis in the Worst Case	49.4	29.6

Table 10 Equivalent propellant mass, equivalent specific impulse, equivalent specific impulse ratio and duty cycle obtained in counteracting y_B -axis torques in the "B" engine configuration case with T_l parallel to the satellite sides.

T_l Parallel to the Satellite Sides	m_p^{TOT}	I_{sp}^{eq}	r [%]	Duty Cycle [%]
τ_y due to T_a	8.49	288	96.1	17.8
τ_y due to T_l	8.23	297	99.1	3.88

Table 11 Equivalent propellant mass, equivalent specific impulse, equivalent specific impulse ratio and duty cycle obtained in counteracting y_B -axis torques in the "B" engine configuration case with T_l diagonally oriented.

T_l Diagonally Oriented	m_p^{TOT}	I_{sp}^{eq}	r [%]	Duty Cycle [%]
τ_y due to T_a	8.39	292	97.2	25.1
τ_y due to T_l	8.20	298	99.4	5.49

Table 12 Equivalent propellant mass, equivalent specific impulse, equivalent specific impulse ratio and duty cycle (only for y_B -axis control) obtained in counteracting x_B -axis torques in the "B" engine configuration case.

	m_p^{TOT}	I_{sp}^{eq}	r [%]
τ_x due to parallel T_l	8.16	299.7	99.9
τ_x due to worst case of T_l	8.36	292.8	97.6

Table 13 Data about the differential thrusting functioning mode of the engines.

	τ_y (T_l Parallel to the Satellite Sides)	τ_y (T_l Diagonally Oriented)
Number of Valve Actions	3743	5213
Operating Time in Monopropellant Mode [s]	112.3	156.4
Total Average Thrust [N]	38.0	38.6
Total Actual Burning Time [s]	632	622
Rotation After One Valve Actuation [°]	0.0046	0.0033

VII. Conclusion

The EARS spacecraft is designed to be recovered on Earth after its in-orbit operations. For a precise re-entry it is necessary to perform a controlled de-orbit burn. For this purpose a green storable HTP-propane bipropellant propulsion system has been selected for development.

In the preliminary design two possible configurations have been compared, one with a single 40 N central thruster and one with four 10 N thrusters placed at the corners of the satellite bottom side. Based on the analysis performed, the selected engine configuration is the second one.

In both cases the control of disturbances around the x_B -axis is performed in the same way through cold gas thrusters.

The main difference between the two solutions was the control of the disturbances around the y_B -axis, which is managed with:

- 1st configuration: cold-gas thrusters
- 2nd configuration: differential steering

As long as the disturbances to be corrected are small (such as those caused by the thrust misalignment), the penalty in specific impulse induced by the use of cold-gas thrusters is still acceptable. However, the penalty becomes too severe when dealing with disturbances of considerable magnitude, such as the one induced by the axial thrust arm with respect to the centre of mass. In fact, the specific impulse of the cold gas thrusters is almost five times lower than the one of the bipropellant engine, therefore the propellant penalty would be too high and would jeopardise the original advantage given by the bipropellant engine. Also the use of cold gas thrusters that exploit the shorter satellite side are to be excluded, since the option of positioning them with a 1 m arm is only available on the two extremes of the satellite along the main axis, thus exploiting a longer arm that produces higher control torques. However, the latter solution still generates too high losses and is more difficult to integrate on the platform. It is thus wiser to exploit the differential steering by switching between mono-propellant and bi-propellant operation, producing a much more limited penalty.

This study was one of the preliminary evaluations on which the first layout of the EARS propulsion subsystem is based. The conclusions that were drawn from this research, and in particular the use of four 10 N bipropellant thrusters, led to the decision of composing the propulsion subsystem by four identical modules instead of one single bigger system. Each of these modules is composed of a HTP tank, a propane tank, fluidics, a bipropellant thruster and an electronic board. This solution allows for ease of production and synergy with other applications, moreover it better fits EARS scope, which includes having systems that are reusable, and that can be refurbished, and thus can be easily taken apart and mounted again.

The results of this study also impacted the development plan of the thruster itself, like the addition of a new testing matrix to investigate the fuel pulsed mode that is used to obtain the differential steering.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank all the partners of the EARS consortium. Special thanks to Mr. Luca Zuanetto of T4i for drawing the EARS spacecraft architecture and providing the related pictures. The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe's research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101082531. Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

References

- [1] Raimondi, V., et al., "The EARS project: a new concept for a reusable smallsat platform." *Presented at ESA 4S Symposium, Palma di Maiorca, Spain, 27-31 May 2024.*
- [2] Barato, F., et al., "Preliminary Design of the European Advanced Reusable Satellite EARS," *ASCEND, 30 July-1 August 2024, Las Vegas, NV, USA, 2024.*
- [3] Barato, F., Paccagnella, E., and Pavarin, D., "Explicit analytical equations for single port hybrid rocket combustion chamber sizing," *Journal of Propulsion and Power* 2020, 36, 869–886, URL: <https://doi.org/10.2514/1.B37992>, 2020.
- [4] Barato, F., Paccagnella, E., and Pavarin, D., "Challenges of Ablatively Cooled Hybrid Rockets for Satellites or Upper Stages," *Aerospace* 2021, 8, 190 URL: <https://doi.org/10.3390/aerospace8070190>, 2021.
- [5] Barato, F., Ruffin, A., Santi, M., Fagherazzi, M., Bellomo, N., and Pavarin, D., "Update on green chemical propulsion activities and achievements by the University of Padua and its spin-off T4i," *Italian Association of Aeronautics and Astronautics (AIDAA) XXVII International Congress, 4-7 September 2023, Padua, Italy. Materials Research Proceedings 37 (2023) 645-653* URL: <https://doi.org/10.21741/9781644902813-140>, 2013.
- [6] Barato, F., Bettella, A., and Pavarin, D., "Numerical Investigation of Pressure-Fed Solutions for Paraffin-Based Hybrid Rocket Motors," *AIAA 2013-3897, 49th AIAA/ASME/SAE/ASEE Joint Propulsion Conference Exhibit, 14-17 July, San Jose, CA, USA.* URL: <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2013-3897>, 2013.
- [7] Kongsberg-Nanoavionics, "NanoAvionics Microsatellite Buses MP42 Datasheet," *NA-DS-MP42-000-R5*, 2023.